

CLIMATIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LOWER AMUDARYA NATURAL GEOGRAPHICAL REGION AND CLIMATE-FORMING FACTORS

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Abstract. The article provides information about the climatic features of the Lower Amudarya natural geographical region. Also, the factors that create the climate in this region and the differences in temperature by region are presented.

Keywords: temperature, continentally, location, condition, factor.

The climatic characteristics of the Lower Amudarya natural geographical region are determined by its location in the central part of the Turan lowland, its distance from the oceans, the absence of orographic barriers, sharp continentally, cold winter, hot summer, lushness and dryness. In the lower Amudarya region, the air mass blowing from the northeast dominates in winter. Winter here is much colder than in other regions of Uzbekistan. The average January temperature is -5.7°C in Urgench, -4.8°C in Chimbay, -5.1°C in Kungrad, and -4.5°C in Nukus. The minimum absolute air temperature varies from -30°C to -33°C . The influence of the air mass blowing from the northeast lasts from October to May. From May, the north and north-west air mass starts and it continues until September. At this time, a local tropical air mass from the south will also affect the air temperature. The summer months in Lower Amudarya are quite hot, the average July temperature is 27.1°C in Nukus, 25°C in Kungrad, 27°C in Takhiatas and 26°C in Chimbay. The maximum absolute temperature reaches $43-44^{\circ}\text{C}$. The average annual temperature is around $10-12^{\circ}\text{C}$. [1,3]. The annual amplitude of temperature in the delta is also not the same. For example, it is 34.0°C in Nukus, 32.9°C in Kungrad and 33.6°C in Chimbay.

The geographical location of the Khorezm oasis, the fact that the surface structure is flat and located in the desert zone are also reflected in the climatic

characteristics of this place. Openness of the territory from all sides, lack of large natural barriers in it creates conditions for easy entry of air masses from the north, northeast and northwest. The dominance of these air masses in the majority of the year has a direct impact on the climate parameters of the study region, i.e. temperature and precipitation regime, wind direction.

The location of the studied area in the interior of the Eurasian continent, far from the seas and oceans, as well as between Karakum and Kyzylkum, causes the climate to be dry and sharply continental. Dryness of the climate is characterized by low humidity and precipitation, while continentally is reflected in large fluctuations in daily, monthly, annual and year-to-year changes in meteorological parameters.

For example, the average amplitude was 33°, the difference between the highest and lowest temperature was 78°. According to the data of meteorological stations of long-term climatic indicators of the region, the average annual air temperature was as follows. 13°C in Urgench, 13.6°C in Khiva, 14.2°C in Tuyamuyin.

A number of zonal and azonal factors are involved in the formation and development of various landscape complexes and their complex morphological structure in the Lower Amudarya natural geographical region. These are lithogenic, hydrogen, climatic, biogenic and anthropogenic factors. Below we will briefly touch on the most important of these factors.

Lithogenic factors. Lithogenic factors (geological structure, lithological composition and relief) play a leading role in the creation and formation of the morphological structure of the natural landscape complexes of the lower Amudarya delta and their components. Taking into account the extremely large role of lithogenic factors in the formation of the morphological structure and components of landscapes, R.I.Abolin (1929) was the first to introduce the term "lithogenic foundation of the landscape" into the geographical literature.

The formation of the Lower Amudarya natural geographical region and its constituent geosystems was the result of tectonic movements to the east of the Ustyurt plateau. It is associated with the accumulation of thick alluvial-delta deposits,

where Amudarya waters flowed during the Quaternary period, in a large tectonic sediment reworked due to erosion processes.

The lithology of the anthropogenic deposits filling the tectonic depression and their mechanical composition, the dynamic development of the Amudarya delta, its morphological structure, the frequent changes of the riverbed, the distribution pattern of the deposits, along the alluvial-delta plane of the river water. In some sections, the parent rocks that form the foundation of the Aral-Sarikamish basin rise up and appear in the form of a residual hilly relief, further complicating the morphological structure of the alluvial delta lowland landscapes and forming residual banal landscape complexes with their own characteristics. Near the city of Nukus, the Amudarya river divides into many branches and periodically changes its riverbeds, forming a valley-river landscape complex.

Hydrogen factors. Hydrogen factors, i.e. surface and underground waters, actively participate in the formation and development of the Lower Amudarya geosystems. The effectiveness of hydrogen factors is so significant that even within the desert zonal geosystems of the Turan lowland with arid climate, introzonal hydrogen landscape complexes have developed widely. The emergence, formation and development of delta landscapes is connected with the formation of alluvial layers by bringing huge amounts of river water every year.

Climatic factors. The role of climatic factors that gradually affect the formation of geosystems of the lower Amudarya plain and the evolutionary change of their structural structure is significant. Climatic factors are primarily the main mechanism that creates various natural geographical processes that have positive and negative effects within the lower landscape complexes. A severe continental desert climate is characteristic of the Lower Amudarya region. Extremely hot (43-44°C), extremely cold winter months (-31-32°C), very low atmospheric precipitation (82-108 mm) affect other geographical components of the region - underground and surface water, soil - has a strong influence on vegetation cover, activation of natural geographical processes, their geophysical and geochemical state.

Anthropogenic factors. Human economic activity has the ability to influence nature in every way, to assimilate it and to build various new anthropogenic landscape systems in its place. Agricultural, sedimentary, irrigation, man-made landscape systems and the most ancient archaeological cultural centers occupying the ancient delta of Amudarya and the upper and middle parts of the current delta were formed and developed under the influence of anthropogenic factors. Anthropogenic landscape complexes created under the influence of anthropogenic factors have a complex morphological structure and separate genesis, similar to natural landscape systems.

Lower Amudarya is one of the driest regions of Uzbekistan. Rainfall increases from 80 mm to 110 mm from the south to the north of the delta. 80-85% of the annual precipitation falls in the winter and spring months. The frost-free period lasts 190-200 days. The sum of temperatures above 10°C in all sections of the delta reaches 4000-4500°. Such a climatic resource provides a favourable opportunity for growing all types of agricultural crops, and cotton is only a quick-maturing variety [5].

In the lower Amudarya, the strength and direction of the wind is not the same everywhere and changes according to the seasons. The average speed of winds is 3-5 m/sec. Northeast winds blow mainly in the cold seasons of the year, while north and northwest winds blow in the warm seasons of the year [2, 4]. In the non-irrigated sections of the Lower Amudarya, the natural moisture reserve accumulated due to atmospheric precipitation in autumn, winter and spring is completely consumed by the second half of April, as a result, ephemeral plants quickly turn yellow and wither from lack of water. This has a negative effect on the biomass of ecosystems from natural pastures.

Thus, the climatic features of the Lower Amudarya natural geographical region are determined by low temperature in winter and high temperature in summer, extremely low atmospheric precipitation, extreme continentality of the climate, and a large number of sunny days. The climate of this region is shaped by its geographic location, seasonal changes in the direction of air masses, the absence of orographic barriers that block air masses, recurring baric depressions, and other factors.

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